

NOLLYWOOD MOVIES AND THE PROMOTION OF THE IGBO CULTURE

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Abstract: This study evaluated selected Nigerian movies and the promotion of Igbo culture by examining the cultural practices in movies that describe the authentic nature of Igbo cultures in the context of their old manifestations. The key objectives were to explore selected Nigerian films as a promoter and storehouse of culture that draws inspiration from village rituals, folklore, and worldviews. The study adopted the qualitative research method with interviews in a focus group setting and individual in-depth interviews. The study was based on Turner's theory of ritual process and Symbolic Convergence Theory, and data were textually analyzed. The research questions were discussed using interview guides after watching the film under study as well as asking participants questions based on their personal experiences. The findings revealed that although respondents shared mixed feelings about the promotion of Igbo culture through film, it was discovered that Nollywood movies not only promote Igbo culture but also do so on actual realities of audiences living in conditions, which acknowledges the fact that Nollywood movies draw from both culture and history, and do so by building 'on existing cultural heritage such as song and dance, the oral tradition both literary and rumors and popular culture'. However, given the nature of movies as a tool for promotion, the researcher recommends that movies take advantage of the viable film industry and do more in the promotion of African cultural heritage.

INTRODUCTION

The emergence of the film industry revealed the uniqueness of movies as a form of popular culture; this popular culture has impacted Nigerians and their culture. What makes movies stand out from other forms of media is their ability to be readily available and affordable so that any group, society, or individual can use it to tell their story, because whoever tells a story controls the narrative, and 'the medium is the message' (McLuhan, 1964). The cinema has evolved from several eras to the Nollywood of today, the era started with colonial era 1903-1960, the independence era, 1960-1972, the indigenization era 1972-1992, and finally, the Nollywood period, 1992 (Onuzulike 2010).

This name Nollywood has a questionable beginning; however, it is accepted to have been derived from abbreviations such as Hollywood and Bollywood. Haynes (2005) contended that it potentially showed up on paper without precedent for an article composed by Matt Stein glass in the New York Times in

2002. There is likewise a well-established conversation about it being the public film industry of Nigeria by film pundits. Balogun (1994) required the foundation of a public film in an article named, "Nigeria merits an Entertainment world", distributed in Day-to-day Times (Haynes, 1995). In 1995, three years after Nollywood started creating, he composed, 'the reasons a public film doesn't exist correspond with the political disappointment of Nigeria as a country' (p.8).

Rotberg shows that 'Nigeria, after all contains more than 250 ethno-phonetic gatherings and around seventy "identities": where Yoruba, Hausa and Igbo represent to some degree around 60% of the all out populace' (2007, p.19). This work's primary focus is on the Igbos and their ceremonies as addressed in Nollywood motion pictures, yet additionally makes reference to Nigeria and Africa in more extensive settings periodically in view of a few particular socially shared characteristics across African countries. Albeit, this on itself can be tricky too; however, occurrences of shared traits really do exist across Africa. Nyerere, Obote and Kenyatta, (ex-leaders of different African drops), once said, as Africans we share a typical past and are persuaded of our normal fates, having a typical history, culture and customs which make our solidarity both sensible and regular. To this end, they demand that our prospects are unavoidably bound together by the indistinguishable yearnings and any desires for our kin and the requirement for comparative endeavors in confronting the errands that lie ahead for every one of our free countries' (1963; referred to in Ngugi, 2005, p.2). These normal legacies, history, culture, customs, and customs are what this postulation would depict as 'communalism' regarding the idea of the Igbo and African societies. It incorporates the substance of the being-ness of Africans or the African-ness of Africans, their reality, and the independence of their qualities. It is the exemplary part of what or what their identity is. (Echekwube, 2003, p.26). It depicts the arrangement of social requests where, in addition to other things, the matchless quality of the local area is socially settled, in the public eye is progressively requested, life is regarded, and religion as culture is a lifestyle. For a biological system like this, everybody is an essential piece of the entire and determines their spot with regard to the local area' (Moemeka, 1998, p.124).

Then again, certain qualities have been settled in by Nollywood in the advancement of culture such as ceremonies. Customs as a focal subject is one of the significant approaches to establishing esteemed local area values, and Nollywood has profited from this approach to acquire crowds' considerations. The powers of nearness and response to relics, as exemplified in Nigerian legends in this manner, are two extraordinary variables that work out in Nollywood's encoding model of creation. Although Nollywood, in view of innovation should be visible to vary from unique conventional people media in their method of creations, yet by having town customs as vital to its storylines, the new media share in the upsides of society media. In this way, as Sirinivas contended, since they are important for the country's social climate, they are solid wellsprings of data for individuals. They order the crowd as intuitive media and are ideal of a two-way correspondence, producing grassroots support and discourse among entertainers and the crowds (2003, p.253). Nollywood films create interest by recounting stories that reverberate with native crowds and Diasporic Africans. Consequently, understanding this pretended oral custom and ceremonies in films assists film pundits in perceiving how the movie producer changes their practice into another innovation (Diawara, 1988, p.13). Hairdresser features

'praising the customary' as an insistence of self-esteem for individuals as well as a showing of their advancement and innovation (Stylist, 1997, p.1). It is this reality that this work investigated the select key customs celebrated in Igbo land and much of the time addressed in Nollywood movies like language, dance, custom, standards, acceptance, ancient rarities, religion, and types of government addressing the critical components of culture.

Thus, this study evaluated the cultural practices in movies that describe the authentic nature of Igbo cultures in the context of their old manifestations by evaluating selected films.

Statement of the Problem

The problem of this study is an evaluation one. It dove into the ideological, philosophical, and all other such idiographic motivations as well as assumptions behind the filmic representation of the basic elements of culture in movies made by Nollywood filmmakers such as Igbo marriage traditions, Igbo language, Igbo traditional beliefs, attire, Igbo known rituals, and symbols that reflect Igbo culture. It was guided by the motivating statement of the problem of discovering how Nollywood serves as a medium of cultural representations as it seems to misrepresent instead of represent the culture. It questioned why such blatant misrepresentation was allowed as they are not a true representation of the culture. The study will however study a select audience to determine the extent of this misrepresentation more than anything else, and this point necessitates this study. Thus, this study evaluates what Nollywood is doing with the promotion of Igbo culture in an attempt to interrogate the conviction that once an oppressed group becomes aware of its cultural as well as political oppression and identifies oppressive myths and stereotypes, it becomes the task of that group to replace their lies, deceptions, and escapist illusions with reality (Gledhill, 1999, p.254). In a general sense, this study explores and questions the characteristics easily deductible about Nigeria and the Igbos in particular by viewing Nigerian films.

Objectives of the Study

The major objective of this study is to explore selected Nigerian films as a promoter and storehouse of culture that draws inspiration from village rituals, folklore, and worldviews.

Specifically, this study seeks to determine:

1. Whether Nollywood movies help to promote the speaking of the Igbo language.
2. How Nollywood movies showcase Igbo marriage traditions.
3. Whether Nollywood showcases known Igbo rituals such as Omugwo, burial rites, age grade, Umuada, Osu (cast system), kinsmen, kingship, Nze n' Ozo, and Egwu (dance).

Research Questions

1. How does Nollywood movies help promote the speaking of the Igbo language?
2. How does Nollywood movies showcase Igbo marriage traditions?
3. How does Nollywood showcase known Igbo rituals such as Omugwo, burial rites, age grade, Umuada, Osu (cast system), kinsmen, kingship, Nze n' Ozo, and Egwu (dance)?

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

Theoretical Framework/Review: The importance of a theoretical framework/review is usually to analyze, describe, summarize, assess, and explain theories. When theories are chosen, the research has

an instant guide that shapes the study to be undertaken. Kirby, S., Greaves, L. Reid, C., 2006). The current study was based on symbolic convergence theory.

Symbolic convergence theory

The theory was propounded by Ernest Bormann, John Cregan, and Donald shields, who dealt with the use of narrative in communication (LittleJohn & Fox, 2005). Bormann, in collaboration with his colleagues at the University of Minnesota, introduced SCT as a framework for discovering, describing, and explaining the dynamic process by which humans come to share symbolic reality. Bormann defines the basic communicative dynamic of symbolic convergence theory as, "the sharing of group fantasies that bring about symbolic convergence for the participants".

It is often regarded as a fantasy theme analysis that offers an explanation of the study of religious overtones present in Nigerian home videos. It highlights the similarities between myths, opinions, trends, and reality presented in movies. Griffin (1991) argues that individuals build a sense of community or group consciousness through symbolic convergence (p.34). It is obviously difficult to make a causal link between the fantasy theme of the movie and the reality of parallel trends in public opinion; however, symbolic convergence theory offers potential insight with at least face validity (Littlejohn & Foss, p.158). This suggests that repeated exposure to the content of home movies on culture and myths could influence an individual's perception of Nigerian culture as well as African culture by extension. Perhaps the best way to evaluate this theory is in its artistry, creativity, novelty, and wisdom of which they are used and combined to evoke the needed reality, thus forming it into a vision.

The repeated usage of fantasy theme theory is the easiest way to recognize it, as it is used repeatedly. To say the least, some themes are so frequently being used, discussed, and well known within a particular ethnic group or community that members no longer need to tell the whole story but rather abbreviate it by presenting just a trigger or a cue that is symbolic. The SCT argues that repeated exposure to the myths and themes of Nollywood movies should influence individual perceptions of Nigerians and the reality of Nigerian culture. Knowing the influence that Nollywood films have on African culture, such an effect is reinforced by the enormous consumption by Africans living in Africa and outside the continents. This theory, therefore, can help in the transfer, storage, and reinvention of culture through its repetitive theme and is thus suitable for this study.

Conceptual Review

Concepts fundamental to this study are the concept of culture, creation and movement of culture, stockpiling of culture through filmmaking, Nollywood by and large, the idea of custom, the idea of the Nollywood entertainment world, and portrayals of Africa in movies: frontier survey among others. A few insightful ascriptions have been made concerning the Nigerian home video, also called the Nollywood entertainment world. This study featured a portion of these attributions, referencing critical thought in every position to arrive at the end results.

Concept of Culture: Culture has variedly been characterized over the ages and across mainlands. It is, as Taylor (1832 - 1917) contends 'a perplexing entire, including information, conviction, craftsmanship, ethics, regulation, traditions, and some other propensities procured by individuals as

individuals from a general public' (referred to in 22 Luzbetak, 2002: 134). To embrace the investigation of Igbo and Nigerian societies in this manner 'through its story address', as Bhabha contends, 'doesn't simply cause to notice its language and way of talking; yet additionally endeavors to modify the calculated item itself, where its positive worth lies in showing the wide scattering through which we build the field of implications and images related with its public life' (Bhabha, 1990, p. 3). In this light, some Igbo ceremonies are concentrated on here according to their nuanced visual and social portrayals in Nollywood as parts of [Nigerian] societies that problematize Western generalizations. By and large, I have seen Turner's (1974, 1982) clarification of the joys of theater, film, and TV as a custom cycle to be especially useful in understanding the spot of Nollywood among Nigerians who resound with its social subjects and storylines to investigate implications in the public. Obviously, there are numerous valuable logical hypotheses of this peculiarity; however, the custom cycle is extremely enlightening, to some degree, since Nigerian and Igbo societies specifically (where this essayist comes from) can be portrayed as a consistent series of ceremonies and are broken down by the use of Turner's hypothesis.

Igbo individuals and their Way of life: For the most part, the Igbos of Nigeria have a considerable number of ceremonies that they celebrate. One of the ways by which these customs are imparted in Nigerian and African culture is by keeping up with union in the way of life that associates the member with more extravagant implications and bigger powers of their local area. Ceremonies in this manner make fortitude as abstract encounters of having a similar significant world that is accomplished by members through the consolidated idea of images used in that. Although one recognizes the impact of westernization and logical improvements in Africa and Nigeria by and large, one actually accepts that the new impacts do not nullify these old ceremonies in individuals' regular day-to-day existence. From sunrise to nightfall, individuals have ways and customs through which they speak with their God or divine beings, predecessors, and neighbors

The five key customs concentrated on here are huge instances of these social festivals covered in the way of thinking and cosmology of the Igbo public. These include the Iri-ji celebration (new sweet potato celebration), Ime Oji service (introducing and presenting of kola nut), widowhood and memorial service customs, emblematic ceremony moving, and religion and love customs. Subsequently, advanced age and silver hair represent satisfied life and intelligence, and they may normally acquire the right to civility and graciousness (Onwubiko, 1991, p. 35); the kola nut is an image of life (Abanuka, 1991, p. 5), which warrants regard as an image of neighborliness among these individuals. In this same manner, these customs and numerous others have implications and suggestions that Nollywood features and which this postulation will endeavor to call attention to in their different structures. In these and their festivals, the expectedness of images has a place with the specific Igbo people group that plans or makes and uses them, since there are occasionally varieties in the festival examples of occasion among the Igbos given the varieties and uniqueness of individual ceremonial foundations.

Nigerian home Igbo Movies: Igbo society is one of the three significant ethnic gatherings in Nigeria. They live in the southeast of the nation and are mostly Christians and a couple of conventional strict admirers. Approximately 18–20 million Nigerians communicate in the Igbo language. The Igbos are expanded in their movies, and the topics are illustrative of stories that reverberate with individuals'

encounters and generally their customs, as broken down in this review. The current Igbo society Hair stylist calls a 'momentary society'. In this setting, she alludes to huge discernment and mindsets framed by outside impacts and factors that play played parts in the elements of the public that incorporate the slave exchange, colonization, mixture of the current day Northern and Southern Nigeria in 1914, outer financial and social relations, exchange, evangelists, schooling, first and second universal conflicts, freedom and the Nigerian-Biafran battle of 1967 - 1970. (Hair stylist, 1997, p. 184). The Igbo society ostensibly is the support of the new Nollywood industry with the screening of the principal Nollywood and Igbo film, *Living in Servitude* (1992), by an Igbo man, Kenneth Nnebue. This is especially recognized from the historical backdrop of the old celluloid filmmaking rehearses in Nigeria during the 1970s and 1980s before the approach of new media advances that are predominantly used in Nollywood, as seen currently in Section one. Igbo films have many distinctive qualities from Yoruba and Hausa films. For Ekwuazi, this is found in 'their subjects, their high creative force and their capacity to convey at a level that quickly holds the feelings spring from a specific Igbo lattice' (2000, p. 133). These Igbo films encode reactions to innovation, urbanism, etc. that are explicitly African, Nigerian, and Igbo. In this way, they are an outflow of the Igbo's forceful business mindset, whose field of action is Nigeria's urban communities and not just the Igbo urban communities' (Haynes and Okome, 2000, p. 76). Most Igbo films are set in the English language (more than the Yoruba and Hausa clans), with a few in the Igbo. This is one variable that gives the movies an edge over others as they contact more extensive crowds both inside and outside Nigeria and comprise mostly what non-public crowds outside Nigeria comprehend as Nollywood films. However, in opposition to this contention, another aspect is that many think the Igbo producers are not enough to advance the Igbo language and societies yet sell them in the wake of a much promoted neocolonial government dissimilar to the Hausa and Yoruba. Ceremonies in Nigerian Igbo home recordings: In the Nigerian entertainment world, Igbo customs are profoundly intelligent about communalism, and this is acknowledged in the films they make. The lifestyle of Nigerians overall and Igbos specifically embrace communalistic ceremonies.

In Nollywood, a few motion pictures exhibit customs, particularly that of the Igbo beginning, and they incorporate yet not restricted to *Favor Me* (2005), *African Legends* (2005), *Celebration of Fire* (1999), *Last Ofala* (2002), *Omugwo* (2004), *Widow* (2007), *Darling* (2004), *Crowning ceremony* (2004), *Things Go to pieces* (1986), *Igodo* (1999), *Idiot at Forty* (2006), *Oil Town* (2001) and so forth. In Nollywood films, this brand of culture comes to light particularly through the festival of ceremonies and celebrations among the Igbos. On many occasions, individuals show their convictions in themselves and in different creatures that incorporate precursors and divine beings. They likewise portray how they live and communicate with each other in hello designs, stylized exercises, trade of labor and products, and the general ways of life of individuals. The thought of being in presence is established on communalism by which each being is viewed as connected with each other. For this reason, life is considered as a power and what influences one individual from the local area influences the other; thus, the thought of connection and more distant family connections are viewed as principal in every single social endeavor.

(a) The Iri Ji Celebration is the new sweet potato celebration committed to the lord of the ranch celebrated among the Igbo clan and another pieces of Nigeria (Ibeh, 2003). It is the festival of gathering in thanksgiving to Mother Earth for giving rich sweet potato. It is a yearly local area custom held at the beginning of the gathering season, for the most part in August. Its other name is the dining experience of Ahiajoku, which customarily means its ancientness in the possession of predecessors who venerated the homestead god. "The design is to thank the sweet potato god (Ajoku) for the collection of sweet potatoes, and it includes the butchering of creatures and spilling of their blood in sanctuaries (Ihu mmuo) with spells and supplications to the sweet potato god for a plentiful reap. Devouring is with cooked sweet potato, chicken, stockfish, nshiko, ugba, usu, and palm wine (Ibeh, 2003: 18). In most Igbo films, this custom is frequently exhibited and reverberates with individuals of the Igbo talking region and some others of Nigeria that hold such functions. In *Things Self-destruct* (1986), which is a film adapted from the 1958 top-of-the-line novel of Chinua Achebe,¹ with a similar title, the dining experience of Iri ji is commended with its corresponding customs and images. The film depicts the heartfelt scene of the climate where Okonkwo and his spouses value the land for a rich gathering and plan for the custom festival of the new sweet potato celebration following a seven-day long haul of harmony and compromise with one's neighbors as cherished in the traditions and customs of their territory, Umuofia. There is an extraordinary presentation of daylight shinning brilliantly as Okonkwo and his spouses work in their homestead. Okonkwo checks his snare and feels glad that he has got 'bramble meat' for the celebrations. The ground is dry, implying the dry season in Igbo land when most ranchers unwind and eat their homestead items for the year while commending the public celebration of harvests, as in the Iri ji custom.

(b) (b) Funerals and widowhood ceremonies

In African cosmology, demise is viewed as a section from the natural residence to the domain of predecessors (Onwubiko, 1991; Ewulukwa, 2002). To cover the departed part appropriately, the living family members have a few ceremonies to perform to empower the quiet section and allow the departed into the circle of their precursors. These customs might vary starting with one local area then onto the next in the way of their festivals, yet they are intended to give a similar importance of compelling entry to the hidden world where the precursors keep on residing as the residing dead to ignore the exercises of their residing family members. For example, in *Things Self-destruct*, the burial service rituals of Ogbuefi Ezeudu perform this confidence in the festival of the soul-changing experience.

(c) The late Ogbuefi Ezeudu was a central cleric of the group, a senior, and a hero. When the merriment have started for his burial service rituals, the town disguises are seen marching the length and breadth of the land around midnight to declare his downfall, as indicated by Umuofia custom. This is the custom approach to sending spirits to drift around the whole local area when an extraordinary occasion occurs. Therefore,, nobody is supposed to be seen outside, particularly ladies and children. The drums are sounded more than once and weapons are shot in a furor. All named older folks courageously accumulate around the compound of the fallen legend, sadly. As custom warrants, they are to offer their final appreciation to him and join the considerations of talking with the prophets on the way of the internment rituals. In this film, Okonkwo strolls in his direction to where Ogbuefi Ezeudu

was laid. There he stopped briefly like a meandering swashbuckler, did a smidgen of moving to the raving strong of the drums and woodwinds, yelled the names of the fallen legend, lifted his firearm, and fired the air. Drums are huge social devices of correspondence in Africa close to the flute, gong, and other conventional instruments, particularly at burial service customs. The 'talking drum' is called Ikoro or Obodom in the southeast of Nigeria.

(d) The Umuada or Umuokpu religion is a public of women brought into the world locally and wedded beyond it. This return at notable periods to their familial homes to participate in town festivities and stylized customs. On such occasions, they wipe the slate clean between neighbors, rebuff people who are off-base, and arbitrate cases between town individuals and different gatherings. They are a huge gathering at the burial service of town individuals; thus, they can validate what is good and bad locally. Established in culture, this gathering controls the widowhood ceremonies on the spouses of expired residents who they think probably added to the passing of their husbands by not taking proper consideration of them. By depending on customs and customs like these, Nollywood addresses these practices. Like Akudinobi thinks, this is social patriotism in real life with respect to the entertainment world, in which movies focus fundamentally on the issues of the country's societies.

(e) The Custom of Kola Nut (Ime Oji): Oji in Igbo alludes to 'kola nut' which in imagery represents solidarity and life, which these networks and each individual that relates to them celebrate while imparting it to neighbors, companions, or visitors. In Things Go to pieces, the custom of offering drinks and kola nuts is performed when Unoka, the dad of Okonkwo, offers supplications to his family place of worship, which is an ordinary Igbo (African) conventional religion (ATR). In Living in Servitude, it is the primary custom celebrated before feasts, considering consulting Andy with the chieftaincy title, as currently discussed. The emblematic motions that show individuals' philosophical temper in the custom of kola nut is seare when a main minister or one of the older adults takes part in the breaking of the kola nut and summons its precursors and divine beings.

(f) Ritual of Confidence and Religion in Love

The Igbos depict's comprehension individuals might interpret God (Chineke) as one who is engaged with their undertakings more like the predecessors communistically. He is called Amama amacha - 'the incomprehensible being', Echeta obi erie ike - 'one who, when recalled injects certainty', Ogbara niti own biri n'onu - 'the quiet being that holds the last discourse', Ogba also known as eye agha - 'the champion who wins fights without weapons' and so on. Religion as a vital part of life is one more fundamental aspect of communalism in conventional African life (Mbiti, 1969, 1990; Uzukwu, 1997; Okere, 1995; Dipio, 2007). Each individual is directed by an individual god, called chi in Igbo like the 'heavenly messenger' in Christian philosophy. As a part of communalism, Mbiti states that 'religion is the lifestyle of Africans' (1969, p.29). There are clear correspondences between the living and the dead directed by the progressive requesting of things as expressed in communalism. Mankind is initially made by the incomparable God who is called Chukwu or Chineke, the God that makes (Yahweh elohim). This is where African customary religion imparts a limit to Christian philosophy that characterizes the three-fold God as 'the being which nothing more prominent than can be imagined (non solemn es quo maius cogitate nequit) however more prominent than everything that could be considered (quiddam

maius quam cogitate set)' (Anselm of Canterbury, in *Fides et Proportion*, No. 14). The idea of God in African communalism is revealed by the names given to Him in African dialects.

The authentic custom and religion of love is seen among Africans in almost every religious ceremony. Since individuals accept that God is a higher profound power engaged with their undertakings as a local area and people, they contact him through a pantheon of different divine beings and minor divinities such as Ala or Ani, the earth goddess; Amadioha, the lord of thunder; Ajoku, the sweet potato god; and other family gods. On the individual level, there is generally an individual chi called Ikenga in Igbo land, which is considered to swim off evil and carry the best of luck to people. This seeing much of the time gets addressed in Nollywood films, particularly in customs that double-cross confidence in God and the divine beings, in the customary settings, yet additionally in portrayals of cutting edge Nigerian culture.

Empirical Review

Studies recommend that Nollywood has been used as a vehicle for the capacity and movement of Nigerian culture with specific reference to Igbo culture. A review was done by Uwah (2009) on *Customs to Movies: A contextual investigation of visual way of talking of Igbo culture in Nollywood films*. 58 members were concentrated as the review set out to recognize a calculated system for grasping the way of life of Africa and Nigeria, specifically, using the idea of 'communalism', to decide the scope of gathering and use modalities of Nollywood items in Nigeria through center gathering interviews as well as to investigate the effect of Nollywood as an industry directly following globalization. In this review, essential examination contended that filmic portrayals draw a great deal of deductions from their cultural societies and sociopolitical real factors. They contend that political and strict issues as they occur in the Nigerian nation are addressed in the movies, and contrasts in race and love styles. Answers that deceive this feeling in the center gathering meetings incorporate explanations like, 'Nollywood discusses Nigerians, even their religions', 'they give us data about what's going on around us and how we live, 'it shows a ton our [Nigerian] societies; even those of the North and their religions, how poor or rich we are, and on occasion they mimic Hollywood', 'It uncovered what's going on [and what they can mean for us tomorrow'. By the end of the review, respondents' activity confirmed Okome's view that a famous crowd arranges and repeats their longings, goals, and dreams unafraid of institutional interruption. This Nigerian movie technique for telling the social and monetary worries of the miserable step by step develops into neighborhood sentiments frequently left unattended in the bigger political agreement of the state' (Okome, 2007, p. 9). Moreover, film watchers accept that the addressed societies have something to do with their public and arrange their place and positions through the movies. From the prior, the explored accepted that respondents are side by side with the designs of the general public, their societies, and institutional ways of life and can decipher the codes once they see them in films. A portion of the engaged gathering meeting featured how one undergrad said, 'the movies depend on our practices, old and current even today, you perceive how the police individuals perform their responsibilities at check focuses, how customary rulers, legislators, ministers and clerics go about their responsibilities without going along with them'. Hence, the review showed that in Nigeria, the entertainment world has essentially shown the capacity of marshaling natural representative

ceremonies of Nigerian and African societies in movies, which assist in creating sentimentality and reverberation in the watchers. The motion pictures plan to uncover the recognizable stories, issues, and upsides of Nigerians and Africans overall. Here, significant all inclusive inquiries into values and implications of life are investigated. Also, by surveying these video films in gatherings, which is the most loved amusement of certain Nigerians, the investigation discovered that the two watchers and makers are attracted to the movies by the reverberation of storylines to their regular socio-social circumstances or what we bring in this review, the Igbos' native [cultural] 'lived-in circumstances' and ceremonial encounters.

Another concentrate by Ugochukwu (2018) was on Igbo Legacy: Nollywood as a sharing stage. The review depended on more than thirty movies delivered/coordinated by Igbo people somewhere between 1991 and 2013. The review features that while the greater part of those movies, created in Lagos, Asaba, Onitsha, Enugu, and Aba, are set in enormous towns, Igbo heroes will generally stick to tribal convictions and continue with most their customary culture. One more concentrate by Onuzulike (2014) on Nollywood video film's effect on Nigeria and other African climate and culture looks at what Nollywood video films mean for Nigerian and other African societies and conditions by associating an oral culture like Nigeria rapidly through the educated stage to participation in the worldwide town. The exploration expressed that it likewise adds to McLuhan's hot-cool model by applying it to Nollywood video films, which is complicated because the term 'video film' suggests a blend of cool (i.e., TV) and hot (i.e., film) media.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In-depth interviews were conducted with respondents individually as well as with social actors in a focus group discussion setting to understand their communication by securitizing their shared assumptions and perceptions (Lull, 1990, p.183/184). The population of this study is projected 22 million people (citypopulation, 2022-3-21) that make up the population of the southeast region of Nigeria. The sample size of the study was 40 respondents who were purposively selected from 22 million projected population (citypopulation, 2022-3-21) from the southeast region of Nigeria. The decision to have this number of respondents was made to avoid over recruiting, which can affect concentration as well as deep case-oriented analysis, and under recruiting, which can affect saturation (Sandwesi, 1995). Ten films were selected based on the criteria that they are from old Nollywood and are epic or contemporary movies that have rich Igbo cultural heritage. There were three focus group discussion made up of eight participants, whereas an additional eight others were individually approached to be interviewed.

The focus group discussion schedule was subjected to face and content validation and vetting by the study supervisors.

The questionnaires were issued by the researcher at the beginning of the focused group discussion and monitored by an assistant. While the interview was carried out individually by the researcher during the focus group discussion after presenting a Nollywood film of 60-90 minutes, participants were also asked questions from personal experiences and what they already know about the Igbo culture. Data were collected from both primary and secondary sources. Data collected were textually analyzed to

conclude. Textual analysis is ideal in cultural studies as it provides diverse readings and meanings that can lead the researcher to explore all other possible angles of the text, bringing diversity to cultural research (Balsel, 2014, p.172). Films fall into the category of things that can be textually analyzed, thus the researcher's choice.

Result Presentation

Research Question 1: How does Nollywood movies help promote the speaking of the Igbo language?

The use of language is also seen at the village square when the wrestling match goes on. In the case of Ijele, the movie and the protagonist were be praised in order to give him courage to continue in his fight, words like ebubedike. Data in this regard shows that epic movies promote the Igbo language. The movie Ijele, Corona, widow, as well as Achabe's adapted novel things fall apart promote the language by using the local native names of people and places, and the way and manner in which actors pronounce these names clearly shows the viewer how these names should be used. In Ijele, you hear something like Oma, Ijele, Obiligwe, and Igwe, which are instant signifiers that would make a viewer instantly relate the names to the language and it sticks over time, and in the way that they use the names, they call it with reverence and with some sort of interpretation some participant said.

Proverbs and riddles have been used extensively, as data uses that Proverbs are the oil used in eating words The Igbos are very good at using proverbs to send a message across, and you would find this often being used in movies. The food is also named in Igbo like when Ijele would bring meat for Oma's family they laugh and say he has brought 'ewi' which is bush rabbit they could have named its English name but they are trying to promote the language hence its native names datas from the FGD2 show. The kings and all titled men and everyone with titled is name in the native language, which is a further indication of the promotion of the Igbo language. Some participants admitted to having learned the few Igbo words they knew through movies because the film is subtitled when a native word is used. There are some things that cannot be said in English, especially when the chief priest wants to consult the gods, he does so in the native language. The gods perhaps do not understand English (Ha ha all languages), and all the gods have native names.

Teacher 1 agreed that although the movies were made in English, you will see a constant mixture of Engigbo thrown in here and there. Someone must say something in Igbo and mix it with English actors like Pete Edochie, Patience Ozokor, and Chika Obi do this no matter the genre of movie they were in, so this is rightly called Engigbo, whereas the best part is movies that come with sub-titles so that even a non-igbo who may be interested in learning the language will understand. The accountant, on the other hand, concluded that movies helping in the learning of Igbo language is not up for discussion because actors slip it in throughout the movie so that even the uninformed will become curious so that is obvious and conscious promotion Igbo language which will therefore help to prevent extinction and misrepresentation.

Research Question 2: How does Nollywood movies showcase the Igbo marriage tradition?

Data in this regard show that respondents were in agreement that the Igbos are highly patriarchal toward marriage tradition and the traditions that surround marriage. The movie coronation betrays this; teacher 2 said, the zoo Nnabuenyi, who was a titled man, snubbed his wife when she tried to encourage him to support his only brother who raised him. He (Nnabuenyi) shouted, asking, 'do you wear a red cap?' (a red cap being a symbol of authority among the zoo titled men) implying that she should not put mouth where she has no business but what wife does not have business with the husband clearly Igbos have no respect to women when it comes to decision making in the family the teacher concluded. The trader, on the other hand, suggested that this example is an indicator of how patriarch Igbo are as regards marriage tradition and the reverence that is given to men as they have the final say in everything that has to do with marriage, including giving out their daughters in marriage, and how they have no say in the families into which they have been married.

Further to the Igbo marriage tradition promoted by Nollywood, Igbankwu, a shop owner, said, it is the way that the Igbos give out their daughters in marriage, the many steps involved and the role of the men in all of it. For us in Enugu, the shop owner continued it has four steps while it delays from community to community these four steps are like the basics. What he said collaborated with what a production manager from focus group 2, who is also from Enugu State, said. In Nigerian weddings, marriage is very important in Igbo culture, and the traditional rites attached to the union are not taken lightly by families involved. Thus, traditional marriages from the southeast part of Nigeria are very festive and colorful and are divided into four main parts which begins with 'Iku aka' or 'Iju ese' the shop owner continued. This is when the male comes with his father and uncles to seek consent of marriage from the bride-to-be's extended family known traditionally as 'Umunna', followed by bride price negotiation and payment known as 'Ime ego' and finally the wine-carrying ceremony by the bride known as 'Igba Nkwu Nwanyi' and 'Idu Uno' which comes with a very big party where the bride and groom can invite friends and family to honor their day. All these must be completed, a student said, and the bride's people must be satisfied before the groom can take away his new wife home. The student shared an experience when his elder brother got married in Imo state, where they had little thing remaining on the list and the umunna refused consenting to the marriage until the father-in-law came to beg them, that the marriage list is not something that must finished immediately and that their in-law is a very young man, it is more important for him to take proper care of their daughter to which they consented in unison and thus the marriage rites were completed.

Research Question 3: How does Nollywood movies showcase known Igbo rituals?

Data in this regard shows that movies promote extensive rituals such as Iri Ji, funerals, widowhood, and Omugu. They go as far as representing these rituals exactly as they would in the physical traditional villages.

Iri Ji Festival, for example, a participant said is the new yam festival that usually comes up between August and September in most Igbo villages. It is a big celebration without which no one is allowed to eat the new yam. It is usually dedicated to the gods as a thank you for fruitful harvest in a given season

and also a way to pray for increase in the coming season. The celebration brings all family members together where they eat and dine with the chief priest or village head offering sacrifice, after which the elders will eat the yam and admit merriment, and thus everyone will be allowed to start enjoying the plenteous harvest.

On the other hand, there is the ritual of widowhood and funerals. Based on the location or the part of Igbo land one may be from, the burial rites may be different; ultimately, they confer reverence and respect for the spirit of the dead relative. When Ogbuefi Ezeudu passed on in *Things Fall Apart*, he was given a befitting burial, which was well documented in the movie. The movie's last burial also showed the burial rites to a large extent, whereas the movie widows exemplified how widows are treated when their husbands die. Some are so bad that the women are made to sleep with their dead husbands bodied, some are bathed and given the corpse water to drink, while some are made to shave their hair and wear a certain type of cloth for the mourning period. In the widow, the young woman was being asked to marry the dead husband's brother who is being tasked to continue the lineage of the man, but she questioned whether death was not enough punishment. The treatment of the dead is a deeply ritual attribute of the Igbo, and people can easily connect with that as they have been to one burial or another.

Another known ritual is that of the kolanut as kids whenever a visitor comes to our house, my mother will bring kolanut served in a sauce pan and hands it over to my dad in which he hangs over to the oldest man to bless and take some if he was not the oldest. This ritual is regularly shown in films. You may think that it is ordinary, but you will notice the same sequence as my dad in our house. This then clarifies to me that it is a known Igbo tradition and a ritual that must be done to receive visitors, but presently people can serve something else other than kolanut. On the other hand, this is a way to show that the visitor is warmly welcomed. Also, kolanut is symbolic ceremonies such as Igbanwu (marriages), child dedication, and the new yam festival. Also, the kind of kola nut will show the respect given to it. One time my father broke a Kolanut, and it was seven parts, he tied it back and waited until there was a special occasion before he brought it out.

Another one is the ritual of faith and belief, which teacher 2 said is to believe in a god that can help destinies and is bigger than all deities. The Igbos are highly religious, and religion is strongly represented in movies. The people pray to adioha or through any medium asking that the little gods intercede on their behalf to the bigger god who is obasi who lives above. They pour libation and believe that every action has a consequence; thus, they present themselves as pure when praying to their gods. A respondent agreed that 'religion is the way of life of the Igbo, and the films have made it a point of duty to show it even before the Christian religion came around'.

Discussion of the findings

➤ Findings revealed that the selected Nigerian films in the review promote the speaking of the Igbo language, which answers research question one (RQ1): does the use of Nollywood films promote the speaking of the Igbo language? In this way, the representation of language in films is a renewal of the celebration of the dominant language used by the Igbos. This is evident in the names that are used for the characters in the movies, how communities are given Igbo names, the way that the attire are named, and how in between rendering lines in English (which is usually the language of communication) by

movie characters some words of Igbo (engligbo) are infused and thus subtitled. Viewers who follow religiously and do not understand the language, although they are locals, reported to have picked up a word or two by watching Nollywood films and retained them over time, and others became interested in learning by consuming the movies. Thus, this finding proves that the symbolic convergence theory, otherwise known as the fantasy theory, is one of the two theories used in this study. Griffin (1991) argued that individuals build a sense of community or group consciousness through symbolic convergence (p.34). It is obviously difficult to make a causal link between the fantasy theme of the movie and the reality of parallel trends in public opinion; however, symbolic convergence theory offers potential insight with at least face validity (Littlejohn & Foss, p.158). This suggests that repeated exposure to the content of home movies on culture and myths could influence an individual's perception and activate learning. Additionally, those who consume Nollywood content tend to learn how to negotiate society's values by engaging themselves actively in the viewing process by accessing their memories and authenticating them through filmic storylines. Teshome argues that, 'once memory enters into our consciousness, it is hard to circumvent, harder to stop, and impossible to run from; it tends to burn and glow from inside, causing anguish, new dreams and even newer hopes'. Beyond telling us how we got here, memory also 'reminds us of the causes of difference between popular memory and official versions of history' (1989, p. 54). This, in order of words, highlights the key important negotiation that audiences in this mode deal with in Nollywood consumption attitudes.

➤ **How does Nollywood movies showcase Igbo marriage traditions?**

➤ Further findings revealed that Nigerian movies show the manner in which weddings and marriages are conducted in Igbo land, which answers RQ2. It provides an avenue for learning and advocacy as it promotes issues in society in such a way that it provokes discussion around that topic, by using satire or humor to drive home serious issues. Data showed that the protagonist in the movie 'burial' was made to marry her dead husband's brother without consideration, her consent or feeling but insisting that tradition is tradition and must be followed, which led to anarchy in the family due to her refusal and subsequently her engaging the audience if death was not a enough punishment for a widow, why should she be subjected to inhumane treatment? Further findings in in this regard show that participants are in agreement that the Igbos are highly patriarchal regarding Igbo marriage tradition, the movie coronation betrays this; the zoo Nnabuenyi who was a titled man snubbed the wife who was trying to encourage him to support his brother participants chipped. He (Nnabuenyi) shouted by asking, 'do you wear a red cap?' implying she should not contribute to their [zoo Nnabuenyi and his poor uncles Okudo] discussion because she is not an zoo titled person in society. These examples indicate how patriarchal Igbo marriage tradition is and the reverence that is given to men. Apparently, Nollywood is showcasing this to bring awareness to these issues as they are still prevalent in some Igbo communities to which the films drew attention. This is made obvious when participants argue that the things shown in Nigerian films are dependent on their lived-in condition; therefore, they happen all around us and serve as lessons. In the same vein, participants highlighted the idea of pleasure in Nollywood movies in their contributions. It is easy for people to determine themselves in Nollywood filmic stories and pinpoint some of their community experiences. Thus, Nollywood films signal the

desire of young people in their intentions for progress in Nigeria to question the dependency on mundane traditions and antiquate them where necessary while retaining only those rich cultural heritages that advance Africa as a continent.

➤ More findings show that the Igbos through the movies reviewed belief in higher beings and in their ancestors, who can intercede on their behalf with Chineke or Obasi bi n'igwe (the god who lives above and these form a greater part of the movies representation and answers research question three (RQ3). In addition, the Igbos believe that *anne di uto* (brotherhood is supreme) it is better to live communally in harmony with one another. Okeke did not go to the *okonkwo* compound at night to watch the moonlight because he couldnot see the moonlight from his compound, but because *igwebuke* (there's strength in unity). They believe that interacting cordially with one another, as seen in greeting patterns, ceremonial activities, exchange of goods and services, and the overall lifestyles of the people shown in the selected movies in review, proves Turner's theory of ritual process valid. This theory highlights how members of a given society represent their communalistic rituals, just like the Ndembe people of North Western Zambia on whom the theory is based. Ritual theory allows people to express what moves them most through their communalistic rituals, and since this form of expression is conventionalized and obligatory because of belonging to the group, the values of the group are revealed (Uzukwu, 1997, p. 41). This no doubt highlights the existence of a group that is founded on communalism where every being is considered to be related to one another. The Igbo belief that living together among kinsmen makes life far better is considered a force and what affects one member of the community affects the other. Hence, the notion of kinship and extended family relationships are considered fundamental in all cultural undertakings and fully represented in Nigerian movies.

Further findings revealed that in Nollywood films culture comes to light by the celebration of rituals and festivals among the Igbos. This answers RQ5 and proves Turner's theory of ritual process to be valid, which as a theory is symbolic in the ways by which members of a given society express their communalistic rituals. He insists that people express their communalistic rituals as what moves them most, and since the form of expression is conventionalized and obligatory, just like burial rites, age grade , etc., it is the values of the group that are revealed (Uzukwu, 1997, p. 41). This notion has been decoded in the select films that bring to light festivals and activities of communities that are symbolically celebrated, which then becomes an integral part of people's acceptable way of life and personalities. A valid example is the funeral rites of titled men and women, new yam festivals, passage of rites being the initiation rites of young adults, naming ceremony of new-born babies, breaking of kola nuts, title-taking ceremonies, and dozens of other ritual events. These are all cultural rituals that Nigerians, especially of Igbo origin, celebrate with symbolic rites, full of significant meanings that are all recurrently represented in Nollywood films. Moreover, this study discovered that Nollywood films express Igbo cultural values in a way that resonates with people's lives and experiences by focusing on their cultural rituals and everyday lived-in situations by highlighting that the themes shown in movies continue to depict Igbo cultural values, language, norms, ideologies, etc. They also communicate to the outside world a more comprehensive representation of the indigenous people's worldviews and way of life.

Conclusion

This study discussed selected Nollywood films and the promotion of Igbo culture. It showed that the film industry has evolved to represent the stories as well as the myths of people with a rich cultural heritage, contrary to the stereotypical visual imagery of African people told by the mainstream cinemas of the West. The themes present in films not only showcase Igbo values but expressly without reservations continue to make a strong statement by letting outsiders know exactly who these people are and how they feel about their world and how the world should feel about them. You see examples in films such as *Things fall apart* on how their community should be seen. Palmer insists that 'Umuofia society is proud, dignified, and a stable community; therefore, it should not be taken for granted because it is governed by a complicated system of customs and traditions extending from birth through marriage to death. It has its own legal, educational, religious, and hierarchical systems, and the conventions governing relations of power between the various generations' (1972, p. 49). This attitude toward them is non-negotiable, and that is how Igbo communities want to be seen, and the film draws a clear map to these attitudes.

This research work has shown that communication involves all humans and extends to the spirit world where the ancestors and the gods have control; hence, the symbolic representation of forces in ritual celebrations as manifested in the films analyzed. The major highlight of the communication as seen in the analyzed films is Moemeka's view that 'in societies, communication is a matter of human interrelationships to confirm, solidify and promote communal social order' (1997; p. 171). Further, actions that show these human interrelationships were seen in relation to rituals and the significance of people's reactions as seen in family relationships and meetings, village markets, funeral occasions as well as religion' (Moemeka, 1997, p. 172). Thus, according to the Igbo culture as highlighted by the movies, it is important to note that communications are not only with living beings, the rituals also show that both ancestors and the gods are considered part of human existence; hence, African communications as represented in the filmic rituals extend to them. In this instance, Des Wilson's work on African society about 'always there is recalling the memory of the ancestors in the past and calling of the people to work together for the future of the community' (2008, P. 51) has been qualified as descriptive of Igbo culture.

Noteworthy in this impressive aspect of Nigerian films in representation of cultural rituals is the ability of the films to marshal out familiar symbolic language of these cultures into their productions, especially in the portrayal of the ritual scenes, to provide the experience of communal liminality (Animalu, 1990, p. 46), cultural integration, and nostalgic egalitarianism among proximate audiences, who are mainly Nigerians at home and abroad as well as Africans in general.

Recommendations

Nollywood is way ahead of its contemporaries, making a global mark over the years in filmmaking, starting with compelling story telling, wide distribution, self-financing, and marketing within and outside Africa in relation to other African film makers. Therefore, the study recommends the following:

➤ Nollywood classic films can be archived in Wikipedia or any other online resource as the case may be, currently such does not exist, only little mentions here and there, meanwhile the world has

gone digital. As such, if a resource is made, it will serve as a reference point, and thus, the movies made can truly be regarded as African stores that can be recalled with just a click.

➤ This online documentation should include all films made by Nollywood filmmakers, their synopsis, cast, crew, costumes, and, in some cases, behind the scenes of how a particular difficult production was achieved.

➤ A physical library dedicated to Nollywood films should be set up either in National theater Lagos or some federal libraries or in collaboration with some institutions of higher learning and such information should be made a public domain.

➤ Film makers should engage the services of historians or go to the local villages, find elders who can share first-hand information on a particular culture in view for their movies and have the elders explain the norms and get an accurate account of events before filming. They should not make the culture depict Africans as unintelligent or less human.

➤ Villagers should not be made to walk barefoot after dressing glamorously in colorful apparel, because this is not a true representation of who the Igbo are. The locals had shoes before the arrival of the colonial master. This needs to be addressed in movies going forward.

➤ Produce more movies that present the Igbos in a positive light, less of bewitching, poverty stricken, elders killing each other, wicked in-laws, native doctors giving wealth to lazy young people who want quick wealth, Igbos are very hard working and go extra miles to patiently build their wealth.

➤ Draw a clear line between the witch doctor and herbal doctor because the latter has been providing healing and medicine for the Igbo way before the colonial masters showed up with the African soul.

➤ Given the nature of movies as a tool for promotion, movies must take advantage of the viable film industry and do more in the promotion of African cultural heritage

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